

Segmenting and Profiling Online Shopping Consumers: How Do They Differ in Hedonic Shopping Motivations?

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to cluster online shopping customers on their loyalty levels and profile them with regards to their hedonic shopping motivations. To this end, a self-administered online survey was conducted, and 226 usable answers were obtained. First, cluster analysis was performed to segment online shoppers on their loyalty values. Later, the final three-cluster solution was profiled according to hedonic value motivations using Generalized Ordered Logit (GOLOGIT) Regression. The two-step cluster analysis revealed three clusters of online shoppers (non-loyals, moderate loyals, and true loyals). The GOLOGIT results indicated that an increase in idea shopping, role shopping, and value shopping of consumers in their online shopping experience would increase their loyalty levels (from non-loyal to moderately loyal, and from moderately loyal to true loyal). With regards to social shopping value, an increase in this dimension would be significantly affective only for non-loyal consumers, increasing their odds of being in the second (moderately loyal) or third (true loyal) cluster. This finding would help in the differentiation of marketing strategies for each segment, which would advance business competitiveness. Considering the increasing importance of online shopping among consumers, findings of this study is expected to contribute to the literature.

Keywords: Online Shopping, Hedonic Shopping, Shopping Motivations, Shopper Segments

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1. Introduction

The roots of hedonic shopping motivation lie in the “entertailing” strategy of retailing industry where retailers try to enhance consumer patronage by providing a fun

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retail environment. However, the global COVID-19 pandemic that has started at the beginning of 2020 has restrained people from retaining their previous shopping habits and has forced them into a new restricted life. Nearly all the countries enforced similar precautions to prevent the spread of the virus such as full shutdown, closure of educational institutions, social distancing and mask-wearing obligations, etc. These restrictions led people to do more activities at home, including the ones that are normally out-of-home activities.

Online shopping is one of these activities which started as the mandatory method of shopping due to the closure of retail stores but then normalised. The increase in the percentage of online shoppers from 36.5% in 2020 to 44.3% in 2021 in Turkey is a sure indicator of this effect. However, this value was 34.1% in 2019 (Turkish Statistical Institute, 2021). The numbers signal that the increase in online shopping due to the global pandemic has become the normal shopping routine for consumers. They were forced to satisfy their consumption needs through online shopping (Koch, Frommeyer, & Schewe, 2020). This obligation, however, was greatly welcomed by them. Online retail platforms provided a convenient alternative shopping channel (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003) and consumers engaged more frequently in this activity (Horváth & Adıgüzel, 2018).

Previous research has revealed the affect of value judgments, both hedonic and utilitarian, on various behavioural outcomes (Cronin, Brady, & Hult, 2000; Rayburn & Voss, 2013). However, most of this research were based on offline consumer behaviour, where it has already been acknowledge that offline retail experience should be enhanced by hedonic experience (Anderson, Knight, Pookulangara, & Josiam, 2014). Related to the pandemic that the world has faced with recently and thanks to the growing importance of online shopping in this period; literature on online retailing and shopping perspectives require further detailing.

The increase in the number and frequency of online shopping has required retailers to create a shopping environment that would satisfy both hedonic and utilitarian consumption needs of consumers. The study of Kaltcheva & Weitz (2006) specially revealed the effect of hedonic motivators, as they found that online shoppers derive pleasure from the shopping experience itself, not from the things they buy. Increasing the perceived value from online shopping experience would result in augmented satisfaction, loyalty, and purchase intention. Raising online traffic would increase online business volume, which is very crucial as attracting and retaining new customers is difficult and costly for all businesses, the same as in online retailing. Hence, it is crucial to understand the factors that affect perception of customers regarding their online experience. This understanding would help better formulation of customer retention strategies. Furthermore, the growing competition between retailers necessitates finding ways of advancing this experience. Knowing what motivates or increases the motivation of consumers towards online shopping would enhance the effectiveness of marketing efforts that retailers present to increase consumer loyalty.

Previous research has suggested that hedonic shopping motivations compose the major part of the urge to shop (Atulkar & Kesari, 2017; Horváth & Adigüzel, 2018). Yet, it requires more evidence of how consumers differ regarding their loyalty levels and which shopping motivations contribute increasing loyalty. In the light of this information, the current study aims to contribute to this field by clustering online shopping customers according to their loyalty and profiling them using hedonic shopping motivations.

2. Conceptual Background

Studies on shopping motivation have started with the work of Tauber (1972) where the author identified that people shop not only for the need of a product or service, but also due to other motivations such as self-gratification, learning about new trends, physical activity and sensory stimulation. The author has grouped eleven motivations under two titles as personal and social motives. This approach was further expanded by Hirschman & Holbrook (1982) who have shifted motivation issue from utilitarian perspective to the hedonic approach and defined it as “those facets of consumer behaviour that relate to the multisensory, fantasy and emotive aspects of one’s experience with products”. Babin, Darden, & Griffin (1994) contributed this approach with the scale they have developed to measure hedonic and utilitarian shopping value.

The studies on shopping motivation were later enriched by the research which extended the scope of shopping motivation to online channels. In addition to the digitalisation brought along with industry 4.0, the recent global COVID-19 pandemic has increased the penetration of online shopping in consumers’ lives. This was a novel approach to shopping and researchers have, therefore, directed their attention to understanding what motivates consumers to shop online, how could consumers be grouped regarding their online shopping tendency and how could this channel be utilized better for the benefit of both consumers and practitioners.

The studies on online shopping motivation and its effect on various behavioural outcomes are, however, limited (Arul Rajan, 2020). Until recently, studies on shopping motivation have dealt with the hedonic and utilitarian aspects in general (Babin et al., 1994; Batra & Ahtola, 1990; Salim, Alfansi, Dart, Anggarawati, & Amin, 2019; Ha, 2020), but it is necessary to comprehend in detail the role of each sub-dimension in leading to behavioural outcomes.

Online Hedonic Shopping Motivation

Babin et al. (1994) have divided shopping value into utilitarian and hedonic dimensions where utilitarian aspects were described as ergic, task-related, and rational. Hedonic value, on the other hand, was referred to as the festive, ludic, or epicurean side

of shopping by the authors. This side included the entertaining and emotional features of shopping. Besides, retailers are more focused on this aspect of shopping motivations (Babin et al., 1994). Consumers are highly involved in their shopping experience and feel escapism during a hedonically valued shopping. Various studies have been conducted which tried to determine the antecedents and consequences of hedonic and utilitarian value dimensions. Jones, Reynolds, & Arnold (2006) tested the interaction effect of shopping value dimensions with satisfaction on several behavioural outcomes, such as WoM, loyalty, repatronage intention, and repatronage anticipation where the findings supported the significant effect of utilitarian value on loyalty and repatronage intentions, and hedonic value on positive word of mouth.

As one of the main drivers of all consumption activities, hedonic shopping motivation was also tested in online retail settings. This channel represents a novel way of shopping (To, Liao, & Lin, 2007). Previous labelling of offline consumers as having both hedonic and utilitarian motivations whereas online consumers as having only utilitarian motivation was invalidated by the current state of online shopping. Together with the technological developments and the global pandemic of COVID-19, consumers started to cast around for alternative shopping channels to offline retailing where they could also satisfy their emotional expectations and experiential needs such as enjoyment, prestige, and sensuality (Parsons, 2002). Furthermore, online shopping provides convenience and time efficiency (To et al., 2007) which also affects opting for online channels.

In addition to the increasing importance of online shopping thanks to technological developments, the global COVID-19 pandemic has shifted this trend to a new level where consumers' shopping habits have permanently changed. Therefore, having a detailed understanding of consumer behaviour in this period and investigating the hedonic reasons people do online shopping would provide novel perspectives about the factors motivating them.

Hedonic shopping value has sub-dimensions that predict behavioural outcomes such as satisfaction, loyalty, purchase intention, and word of mouth communication. The emotional aspects of the shopping process such as enjoyment, escapism, and involvement that consumers experience increase these behavioural outcomes. These emotions “deposit affective memory traces” (Walsh, Shiu, Hassan, Michaelidou, & Beatty, 2011) which turn into positive behaviour of consumers, such as loyalty (Walsh et al., 2011).

Hedonic Motivations

Arnold & Reynolds (2003) have developed a six-factor structure of hedonic shopping motivations which consisted of adventure, social, idea, value, gratification, and role motivations. *Adventure shopping* indicates feelings of adventure, excitement, and stimulation. Consumers describe their shopping experience as escaping from daily

routines and going into another world. It “captures the experiential and fantasy aspects of shopping” (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003). Hedonic customers with high adventure motivation are involved in the search of product or information (Babin et al., 1994) as the product itself is not the only thing that provides sensual joy to consumers during the shopping process (Sherry, 1990).

Social shopping motivation means the enjoyment that shoppers experience while they shop together with friends or members of family (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003). The concept was first introduced as a shopping motivation in offline settings, but later extended to the online shopping context (Wu, Huang, Chen, Davison, & Hua, 2018). The value that consumers ascribe to shopping with family and friends in brick & mortar stores has now turned into the social ties that they establish with online ties in online communities.

The *idea shopping* dimension of hedonic motivation refers to shopping with the intent to keep up with recent trends, to be informed of new products, and fashion (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003). Online shopping provides consumers with this opportunity, and gives information on brands, products, etc. (To et al., 2007). The huge amount of product and brand information in online settings provides consumers the chance to search, review and compare the information at their convenience. For some consumers, getting this information is the end itself (Bloch, Ridgway, & Sherrell, 1989).

Value shopping indicates “shopping for sales, looking for discounts, and hunting for bargains” where shoppers regard the process as “a challenge” or “a game” (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003). This bargain perception fills consumers with hedonic feelings, which in turn increases their involvement and enthusiasm (Babin et al., 1994). Furthermore, getting a discount makes consumers feel as smart shoppers (Chandon, Wansink, & Laurent, 2000). Online shopping provides this opportunity to consumers as they can find bargains and discounts easily.

Gratification shopping is about relieving stress, and getting rid of negative emotions (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003). Consumers indicate that they do shopping to forget their problems, and to relax. Babin et al. (1994) refer to shopping value as self-gratifying for the consumers who consider the shopping process as a revivescence from negative feelings. Gratification shopping satisfies consumers’ desire to escape from reality and makes them feel better.

The final dimension of hedonic shopping motivations is *role shopping* which refers to enjoyment experienced by shoppers when they buy something for others (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003). Buying something for family or friends, finding the correct gift for them is particularly important for shoppers and this activity makes them feel good. It enables them to act the role they are playing. Some of the consumers

experience hedonic value from the shopping process, while some shoppers even consider this process “as an expression of love” (Otnes & McGrath, 2001).

Loyalty in Online Shopping

Loyalty is defined as “a deeply held commitment to rebuy or repatronize a preferred product/service consistently in the future, thereby causing repetitive same-brand or same brand-set purchasing, despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behaviour” (Oliver, 1999). The literature provides ample studies on the mechanisms leading to loyalty, its antecedents, and consequences (Al-Hawari, 2022; Santo & Marques, 2022; Li, Liu, Lee, & Huang, 2019; Pereira, Salgueiro, & Rita, 2016; Toufaily, Ricard, & Perrien, 2013). However, the research on this behaviour in online settings is limited (Srinivasan, Anderson, & Ponnnavolu, 2002; Kim, Jin, & Swinney, 2009; Wong & Haque, 2021). As stated above, the global COVID-19 pandemic has changed consumers’ behaviours permanently. A similar impact is assumed with the online loyalty of consumers.

Online loyalty is a recent concept where there is still a controversy regarding its definition (Ruiz-Molina, Gómez-Borja, & Mollá-Descals, 2021) and it is referred to as the “repeat purchase or intended return visits to a website” (Cyr, Bonanni, Bowes, & Ilsever, 2005). Whereas a traditional seller-buyer relationship occurs in offline retail stores, the communication in online settings is through a website (Cyr, 2008) or an application, which is assumed to affect consumer behaviour and the factors that lead to it. And it is more difficult to establish loyalty in an online setting as it is quite easy for consumers to switch between retailers. Previous studies have revealed the determinants of online loyalty. Haverila, Haverila, McLaughlin, & Tran (2022) found that online loyalty programs, tangible rewards, and brand engagement positively influence online loyalty; whereas Caruana & Ewing (2010) concluded that corporate reputation, perceived value, and website design have a positive and significant effect on online loyalty. Moreover, variables such as brand image (Kwon & Lennon, 2009), relationship quality (Chen & C.S. Ku, 2013), and perceived risk (Hsieh & Tsao, 2014) affect the online loyalty of consumers. The comprehensive review of Toufaily et al. (2013) has grouped determinants of online loyalty as customer-, product/service-, company-, environment- and website-related factors, and they have suggested the analysis of shopping motivation to understand consumer behaviour better in online channels.

In the light of the above-mentioned literary findings, the main purpose of this paper is to segment online shopping consumers based on their loyalty and to describe the segments using hedonic shopping motivations. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

3. Methodology

Participants and Procedure

To collect the data, a self-administered online questionnaire was used during the nationwide curfew during August-September 2021. This method was considered appropriate not only due to pandemic restrictions that prevent carrying out face-to-face surveys, but also it aligns with the theme of the study. The link to the survey was distributed through social networking sites using the snowball technique. A selection criterion of having made online shopping was set to obtain answers from participants who have previous experience in online shopping. Participation was completely voluntary, and no incentive was given to complete the questionnaire.

Before starting the survey, the final version was pretested on ten people to check the wording of the items and ensure that the items are understood as intended. In total, 226 participants completed the survey. Fifty-four percent of the participants were female; nearly 60% were married; 54% were aged between 20 and 29; 50% were at middle income level.

Instrument Design

The questionnaire had two main sections. The first part consisted of demographic questions (gender, marital status, age, and average personal income). The second part included the 5-item e-loyalty (Sheng and Liu, 2010) and 18-item hedonic shopping motivations (Wang et al., 2021) scales that were adapted from prior research. Both scales were measured with five-point Likert-type scales and were coded as 1 indicating “strongly disagree” and 5 indicating “strongly agree”. To prepare the Turkish version of the questionnaire, the scales were translated into Turkish by a forward-backward translation procedure. The final version was tested with a small sample of participants to ensure that the items are understood as intended.

Data Analysis

The data analysis procedure had four main steps. First, the data were screened for assumption testing (i.e. multivariate normality, linearity, and homoscedasticity). After ensuring that the data is suitable for further analysis, the validity and reliability of the scales were tested. In the third phase, a two-step cluster analysis was used for the segmentation of the dependent variable (loyalty). In the final step, generalized ordered logit (GOLOGIT) regression was administered to find out how clusters differ from each other with regards to descriptor variables (role shopping, value shopping, idea shopping, and social shopping).

4. Results

Assumption Testing

The data were screened for missing values first and were replaced with the series mean. Generalized ordered logit regression requires multicollinearity, model specification, and parallel regression assumption. Due to the nature of the dependant variable, homoscedasticity and multivariate normality assumptions are not tested (Mert, 2016). VIF values of the variables were calculated to check for multicollinearity and all of them had values less than 2, which indicated that the variables do not have multicollinearity. The assumptions of model specification and parallel regression were tested with STATA while running the analysis.

Reliability and Validity Assessment

An exploratory factor analysis was made with SPSS to determine the factor structure of hedonic shopping motivations and to check for the uni-dimensionality of loyalty. Using varimax rotation, items with factor loadings less than 0.5 and cross-loaded items were eliminated. The elimination procedure resulted in a four-factor solution for hedonic shopping motivations where the sub-dimensions of adventure seeking and gratification were eliminated and therefore were not included in further analysis. An item from gratification was loaded onto role shopping dimension and it was evaluated as acceptable considering the subject it tries to measure. The final four-factor solution, where each one had eigenvalues greater than 1, explained 77.7 percent of the total variance. The Kaiser–Meyer– Olkin measurement of sampling adequacy was 0.848, and Bartlett’s test of sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 1794.185$, $df = 78$, $p < 0.001$).

With regards to loyalty, the EFA results indicated a single-factor solution where all factor loadings are above .70, explaining 71 percent of the total variance (KMO=.867; Bartlett’s test of sphericity: $\chi^2 = 654.402$, $df = 10$, $p < 0.000$).

Cronbach's alpha was used to measure the reliability of the factors together with composite reliability (CR). All Cronbach's alpha values and CR values were above the accepted level of .70 (Nunnally, 1978), indicating that the scales were reliable. Average Variance Extracted values were also calculated and were found greater than the recommended minimum value of .50 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The descriptive statistics, and final factor structure obtained from EFA, Cronbach's alpha, CR, and AVE values are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics, EFA loadings, AVE, CR, and Cronbach's alpha values

Factors	Items	M (SD)	Overall M (SD)	Factor Loadings	AVE	CR	α
Role shopping	GS4*	2.95 (1.28)	3.28 (1.02)	.718	.619	.866	.874
	RS1	3.33 (1.22)		.879			
	RS2	3.45 (1.15)		.768			
	RS3	3.38 (1.16)		.774			
Value shopping	VS1	3.74 (1.10)	3.62 (1.02)	.851	.690	.869	.857
	VS2	3.56 (1.20)		.814			
	VS3	3.58 (1.16)		.827			
Idea shopping	IS1	2.65 (1.18)	2.81 (1.07)	.847	.687	.867	.873
	IS2	2.70 (1.20)		.885			
	IS3	3.08 (1.20)		.750			
Social shopping	SS1	2.25 (1.05)	2.30 (0.94)	.830	.713	.881	.854
	SS2	2.36 (1.08)		.860			
	SS3	2.29 (1.08)		.844			
Loyalty	Loy1	3.48 (1.02)	3.37 (0.88)	.784	.566	.906	.898
	Loy2	3.35 (1.08)		.851			
	Loy3	3.20 (1.05)		.871			
	Loy4	3.46 (1.04)		.857			
	Loy5	3.38 (1.06)		.848			

Notes: AVE = Average Variance Extracted, CR = Composite Reliability, α = Cronbach's Alpha

*The question from gratification dimensions

Source: Authors' calculations

Cluster Analysis

To create homogeneous subsets of participants according to their loyalty levels, a two-step clustering analysis was performed. Previous studies have also employed cluster analysis to create unique segments among participants (Allaway, Gooner, Berkowitz, & Davis, 2006; Coşkun & Yetkin Özbük, 2019; Prayag, 2012; Styliadis, Woosnam, & Ivkov, 2020; Tanford & Baloglu, 2013). First, hierarchical cluster analysis was conducted using Ward's method. Examination of the dendrogram and agglomeration coefficients was followed by a k-means cluster analysis of participants

as the second step to obtain an improved solution. Three clusters were determined, and the participants were compared with further analysis using their hedonic motivations.

Comparison of Clusters with Generalized Ordered Logit (GOLOGIT) Regression

The three clusters that were obtained from the clustering analysis were labelled upon the mean scores of loyalty levels (Table 2).

Table 2. Mean scores of clusters

Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Non-loyals (n=26)	Moderate loyals (n=72)	True loyals (n=127)
1.65	2.87	4.02

Source: Authors' calculations

The first cluster with the least loyalty mean was labelled as non-loyals and they constituted about eleven percent of the participants. True loyals with the highest loyalty value formed more than half of the participants. And the third cluster, comprising about 30 percent of the participants, was named as moderate loyals and this group had a mid-level mean value of loyalty.

After clustering the participants according to their loyalty values, they were compared with regards to the hedonic shopping motivations. The mean score for each segment is presented in Table 3, where non-loyals have the least scores for each of the hedonic shopping motivations whereas true loyals have the highest value in each dimension. To test the difference within groups, a generalized ordered logit model (gologit) was employed. As the assumptions of ANOVA could not be met, and clusters had ordinal levels, ordered logit regression was used instead of a non-parametric test. Yet, the Brant test for proportional odds assumption was invalidated by some of the variables ($\chi^2(4) = 55.03, p=0.000 < 0.05$), and the Wald test results displayed that social shopping value was violating the proportional odd assumption. This finding led to employment of generalized ordered logit (GOLOGIT) model (Mert, 2016; William, 2006).

Table 3. Loyalty mean scores of clusters for hedonic motivations

Hedonic motivations	Cluster 1 Non-loyals (n=26)	Cluster 2 Moderate loyals (n=72)	Cluster 3 True loyals (n=127)
Role shopping	2.30	3.11	3.57
Value shopping	2.73	3.41	3.93
Idea shopping	1.91	2.64	3.09
Social shopping	1.48	2.31	2.47

Source: Authors' calculations

GOLOGIT model was estimated by using STATA software. Previous tests of independent variables indicated that there was not any multicollinearity problem. The model specification was tested with linktest (hatsq: $p = 0.620, >0.05$), revealing a well-specified model.

Table 4. Generalized ordered logit model results

Independent variables	MODEL			SET 1: Cluster 1 vs Cluster 2 &3			SET 2: Cluster 1&2 vs Cluster 3		
	Coef.	p-value	Odds Ratio	Coef.	p-value	Odds Ratio	Coef.	p-value	Odds Ratio
Social Shopping				1.167	0.001*	3.360	0.137	0.464	1.145
Value Shopping	0.443	0.007*	1.558						
Idea Shopping	0.307	0.062**	1.360						
Role Shopping	0.317	0.072**	1.373						

N=225, LR $\chi^2=65.39$ ($p=0.000$), Pseudo $R^2=0.15$
* $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.10$

Source: Authors' calculations

The results of the logit effects reveal that the logit regression coefficient for value shopping was significant at 95 percent reliability ($\beta = 0.443$), and idea shopping and role shopping were significant at 90 percent reliability ($\beta_{ideashopping} = 0.307$; $\beta_{roleshopping} = 0.317$). The meaning of these findings is that the odds of being more loyal (becoming moderate loyals from non-loyals or becoming true loyals from moderate loyals) were 1.558 time greater with one unit increase in value shopping motivation of consumers. Similarly, a one unit increase in idea shopping and role shopping motivations of consumers would increase their odds of being more loyal 1.360 and 1.373 times, respectively. It was mentioned above that proportional odds assumption was violated for social shopping motivation. The logit coefficient was found significant only for the first set ($\beta = 1.167$) which indicates that a non-loyal consumer engaging in social shopping motivations would increase his odds of being a moderately loyal or loyal consumer 3.360 times more.

5. Conclusion and Discussion

The purpose of this research was to profile online shoppers, who were clustered according to their loyalty values, with regards to their hedonic value motivations. Determining the hedonic motivations that affect loyalty levels of customers in their online shopping experiences, especially since customers turn to online shopping during the Covid-19 pandemic, is considered crucial as customers with high hedonic motivations have a higher impulse to buy, spend more time in stores, shop more (Yim, Yoo, Sauer, & Seo, 2014) and are more loyal (Nguyen, Nguyen, & Barrett, 2007; Tyrväinen, Karjaluoto, & Saarijärvi, 2020). Two-step research was thus designed. The findings indicate that online shoppers are grouped into three distinct segments as non-loyals, moderate loyals, and loyals. Next, the hedonic value motivations provided the

attributes of each segment. In addition to confirming previous research on the effect of hedonic value motivations on loyalty (Amirtha & Sivakumar, 2021; Luo & Ye, 2019), this study validates the effect of these motivation dimensions on distinct loyalty segments of online shoppers.

The first contribution of the research is to segment online shoppers using their loyalty values. This effort has been made before by previous research using demographic and psychological characteristics (Chocarro, Cortiñas, & Villanueva, 2015; Pandey & Chawla, 2016). The contribution of the current study is to frame each segment with dimensions of hedonic motivations. Previous research findings on online shopping revealed that the shoppers who enjoy the process as a leisure activity have a more positive attitude towards online retailing (Bridges & Florsheim, 2008). This finding supports the prominence of hedonic motivations in shaping various behavioural outcomes of consumers. Consumers having a more advanced experience would be more loyal to the online store, and this fact would turn into more online buying. Therefore, it is crucial to analyse consumer segments in detail, which is a contribution provided by the current research.

Our findings verified the significant difference of loyalty segments with regards to their value shopping behaviour. An increase in value shopping motivation would result in higher loyalty levels. When consumers experience discounts or low prices during their purchases, they would consider themselves as smart shoppers and this would in turn lead them to shop more online meaning that they would be more loyal to the e-retailer. The vast usage of online retailers has directed consumers to look for the best bargain. Therefore, providing this opportunity for shoppers would increase their loyalty. Thus, the current research finding contributes to the previous research which has supported the effect of value shopping motivation on different behavioural outcomes (Akram, Hui, Khan, Yan, & Akram, 2018; Atulkar & Kesari, 2017).

With regards to idea and role shopping, the study results were also significant ($p < 0.10$). Idea shopping motivation is about finding out the recent trends and fashions that consumers would like to keep up with. Online shopping provides this opportunity to consumers in the most efficient manner. They could easily and quickly search different retailers for the latest products and brands within the comfort of their homes. Web retailers would perform better than physical retailers in the chances of learning new trends and innovations (Parsons, 2002). The results indicate similar findings with previous research suggesting that an increase in idea shopping motivation of consumers would lead to transferring to a higher loyalty level (Luo & Ye, 2019). Similarly, role shopping was found significant ($p < 0.10$). Role shopping is about the joy that shoppers experience when they buy something for significant others. Consumers feel positive when they find the best suiting gift for their family or friends. Online shopping eases this process by giving the shoppers the chance to surf through the alternatives quickly and easily and find the best present. Our findings also supported this fact, indicating that an increase in role motivation of shoppers would result in higher loyalty levels (Nguyen et al., 2007).

With regards to social shopping, which is about socializing and bonding with other people while shopping, previous studies verified the effect of sharing shopping experiences with others on various behavioural outcomes (Moharana & Pradhan, 2020). In terms of online shopping, this hedonic motivation derives from the pleasure that shoppers get when they share their shopping experience through a social network, recommend or comment on products. “Netizens share their buying experience on online blogs and become socialized through this activity” (Akram et al., 2018). The findings of the current study on the effect of social shopping motivation on loyalty revealed its discriminating role between non-loyals and the other two segments (moderate loyals and true loyals). It means that a significant increase in social shopping motivation of online shoppers would results in loyalty of consumers.

Managerial Implications

The above-explained findings suggest several courses of action for practitioners. The first issue relates to segmentation of online shoppers according to their loyalty values. This segmentation would allow applying more advanced marketing strategies thanks to a deeper understanding of the loyalty levels of shoppers. It would help marketers with identifying the factors to be controlled and to be improved, leading to a more competitive business strategy. Research findings suggest that traditional and online store shoppers are more similar than they are thought to be (Ganesh, Reynolds, Lockett, & Pomirleanu, 2010). Today, retailers try to design online stores just like physical ones so that online shoppers would experience the same joy, involvement, freedom, and escapism as physical store shoppers. Thus, enhancing the online retail environment by learning the critical success factors would enable directing the resources to where they are needed most.

The second issue about the findings of the current study is on profiling customers. Using hedonic motivation dimension, online shoppers in loyalty clusters were tried to be pictured. This finding would assist online retailers in centering their positioning strategies according to hedonic motivation of shoppers, which would lead to creating a difference between online and offline stores not only in terms of physical or utilitarian aspects but also on personal motivations of shoppers. If online retailers enable shoppers to experience the opportunity of smart shopping through discounts and promotions, the feeling of doing something good for significant others, to socialize through online networks through the recommendations and comments they make, and to follow the recent trends and innovations, they can build or increase the loyalty of their consumers.

Limitations and Further Research

Several important limitations need to be considered for the current study. First, only loyalty was used to cluster online shoppers and limited variables were used to

profile them. Further research employing other psychographics (e.g. personality, lifestyle, social status), demographic (e.g. gender, education, income) and other behavioural (e.g. recommendation, usage rate, WoM) factors would deepen our understanding of consumer behaviour in online shopping. Second, the study is limited to consumers from a single country, which overlooks the effect of cultural differences. So, replicating the research in other countries would further validate the findings of the current research. Finally, the sampling method of the research lacks its generalisability, as the participants were not randomly selected. More bordered research would both overcome this limitation and help drawing a detailed segmentation of online shopping consumers.

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